

AN INVESTIGATION ON COMPOSITE CONSTITUTED OF PAPER AND RESIN BY VENT-TYPE INJECTION MOLDING MACHINE

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ABSTRACT

The objective of this research is using composite combining with plastic and paper materials to relieve the depending on timber from ecological thinning. Therefore, the property of the composite is needed to be investigated. It is considered that two kinds of properties need to be investigated including mechanical property and thermal property. At present study, the direct fiber feeding injection molding(DFFIM) process was used to fabricate composite materials. Poly ethylene (PE) was used as matrix. The crushed paper (CP) fibers and paper powder (PP) were used as reinforcement. The dumbbell specimens were fabricated by injection molding machine prepared for mechanical property and thermal diffusivity measurement. Static tensile and bending tests were conducted by an Instron type universal testing machine. The constant speed of cross-head was 1 mm/min. The Izod impact test was also conducted. Both pure resin and paper FRP were tested in this research. It was found that the tensile property was increased after combined with paper fibers. A TC-7000 (ULVAC, Inc.) laser flash method thermal measuring apparatus was used to measure the thermal diffusivity. This system directly measures the thermal diffusivity and specific heat capacity by heating one side of a disk sample with laser flash and detects the temperature response curve of the back side. From the thermal diffusivity test, it was found that the thermal diffusivity was increased after adding paper fibers into PE resin. The scanning electron microscope (SEM) observation was also conducted to evaluate the fracture behavior on paper composite.

1 INTRODUCTION

Recently, the environmental protection has become a hot topic. Ecological thinning is a silvicultural technique used in forest management that involves cutting trees to improve functions of a forest other than timber production. However, it has a limitation of quantity to get timber from ecological thinning. This become a problem to products made from this kinds of wood in the future. The objective of this research is using composite combining with plastic and paper materials to relieve the depending on timber from ecological thinning. Therefore, the property of the composite is needed to be investigated.

For the property of composite, two aspects need to be investigated including mechanical property and thermal property. In the previous research, the mechanical property of paperboard composite was investigated. Three types of unsaturated polyester resin were used to improve properties of recycled paperboard. The resin can help not only to improve the resistance to water but also to enhance the mechanical property. Tensile test, short beam bending test and drop impact test were carried out to

evaluate the mechanical property of paperboard composite. It was found that the mechanical property increased obviously. It is an effective to improve the mechanical property of paperboard to instead of wood products. From the optical observation results, it was considered that the impregnation was an important factor to improve the mechanical property of paperboard composite [1]. The mechanical and physical properties of single layer particleboards made with various ratios of waste paperboard fibers to wood particles was investigated by Amir Eshraghi and Habibollah Khademieslam [2]. Urea formaldehyde resin was also used as adhesive in different amounts of 9% and 10%. Static bending strength, internal bonding and thickness swelling were measure during the study. The results revealed with increasing waste paperboard fiber content up to 50%, the modulus of rupture and modulus of elasticity of the panels increased. All the physical and mechanical property improved by increasing the amount urea formaldehyde resin [2].

In most physical and chemical processes, heat transfer and temperature change occur. Thus, thermal conductivity, a fundamental property that dominates a material's behavior in heat and temperature transferring processes, must be taken into account [3]. For example, wood is the common materials to make stick for ice cream due to its low thermal diffusivity. In the research of G. Wrobel at el., the thermal diffusivity of carbon fibre/epoxy composites with different fibre content was studied by using flash method. The experiments have been performed using transient thermography to obtain the thermograms for carbon/epoxy specimens with different carbon fibre content. From recorded thermograms the thermal diffusivity values were determined for two different heating conditions to verify the effect of heating conditions on thermal diffusivity values. It was found from obtained results that composites with different carbon fibre content had different values of thermal diffusivity. Relationship showed that the thermal diffusivity is linear function of carbon content in considered materials [4].

At present study, the injection molding process was used to fabricate composite materials. Poly ethylene (PE) was used as matrix. The crushed paper (CP) fibers and paper powder (PP) were used as reinforcement. Tensile property of pure resins and paper fiber reinforced plastic (FRP) was investigated as well as bending and Izod impact test. Thermal conductivity of paper FRP was investigated by the laser flash equipment. It was found that the tensile property had slightly decreased after combined with paper fibers. Thermal conductivity test showed was increased after adding paper fibers into PE.

2 MATERIALS AND EXPERIMENTS

2.1 Direct fiber feeding injection molding (DFFIM)

In general, compounding process is often used to fabricate the pellets materials which will be use for the injection molding process. And this process usually costs more energy and consumes a lot time. Direct fiber feeding injection molding (DFFIM) technology is considered to short-cut the production processing and reduce energy consumption.

Figure 1 The schematic of direct fiber feeding injection molding

As shown in figure 1, the continuous filaments can be fed into the barrel of the injection machine from the vent window and the resins can be fed from the hopper of the injection machine. One or several fiber bundles can be fed continuously and stably to get different fiber contents of composites. Resin feeding speed can be controlled by the hopper. During the processing process, the vent window can eject vapor if the paper fiber or powder is not so dry.

2.2 Materials

Two kinds of paper materials were used in this research, included crushed paper fibers and paper powder. The photos of paper materials is shown in figure 2.

Figure 2 Crushed paper and paper powder

Materials	NO.	Fiber content wt%	Materials	NO.	Fiber content wt%
PE	PE	0		CP1	6.67
Paper powder & PE	PP1	6.67	Crushed paper fiber & PE	CP2	13.3
	PP2	13.3		CP4	26.7
	PP4	26.7		CP6	40.0

Table 1 The component of composite materials

The fibers and powder contents were controlled during injection process. The fiber contents of each material are listed in table 1. During injection process, paper powder is more difficult to fabricate composite compared with crushed paper fiber and it is very difficult to inject 40.0% of paper powder composite.

The fabricated specimens of paper fiber or powder reinforced PE composite is shown in figure 3. As the contents of paper contents increasing, the color become darker. From the low fiber or powder contents specimen such as PP1 and CP1, many small dark point could be found in the specimen. It is considered that the dispersion of crushed paper fiber in composite was not so good compared with paper powder specimens.

Figure 3 The paper composite

2.3 Experiments

Tensile test was conducted by using an Instron universal testing machine under a speed of 1 mm/min. An extensometer was used to measure the strain during tensile process. The bending test was also performed by using the universal testing machine under a speed of 1 mm/min. The dimension of the specimens was 60×15×3 mm and the span was 48 mm. Izod impact test was performed on the

Impact Tester (Toyoseiki), pendulum 5.5J, in accordance with ASTM D 256-05. The size of the specimen was 10mm×60mm, V-notch was used: the angle of the notch was 45 °.

A TC-7000 (ULVAC, Inc.) Laser flash method thermal measuring apparatus was used to obtain the thermal conductivity. This system can directly measure the thermal diffusivity and specific heat capacity by heating one side of a disk sample with laser flash and detects the temperature response curve of the back side.

Formula (1) is used to calculate the thermal diffusivity.

$$\alpha = 0.1388 \times \frac{L^2}{t_{1/2}} \quad (1)$$

Where, α is thermal diffusivity; L is thickness of specimen; $T_{1/2}$ is half time to reach the maximum temperature. After obtaining the thermal diffusivity results, together with the specific heat capacity results the thermal conductivity can be calculated by formula (2).

$$\lambda = \alpha \times c \times \rho \quad (2)$$

Where λ is thermal conductivity, α is thermal diffusivity, c is specific heat capacity and ρ is density of materials.

3 RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

3.1 Tensile property

Tensile property as a basic mechanical property was tested for all type of specimens. The stress-strain curve of paper fiber or powder reinforced composite is shown in figure 4. As the fiber or fiber contents increasing, the materials becomes brittle. The breaking elongation of 40.0% of paper fibers specimens has the lowest breaking elongation (0.02).

Figure 4 Stress-strain curve of paper fiber or powder reinforced composite

The results of tensile test in different fiber contents are shown in figure 5. Here, CP and PP represent crushed paper fiber and paper powder reinforced composite. These results reveals that modulus increased as the fiber contents increased. However, as the fiber contents increased, the increasing of tensile strength is not so obvious.

A Young's modulus of different fiber contents composite

B Tensile strength of different fiber contents composite

Figure 5 Results of tensile test

3.2 Bending property

The bending results is illustrated in figure 6. From these results, both bending modulus and bending strength increased with increasing of fiber contents. Although crushed paper fiber and paper powder has different dimension, both bending modulus and bending strength of these two kinds composite expressed very close property.

A Bending modulus of different fiber contents composite

B Bending strength of different fiber contents composite

Figure 6 Results of bending test

The fracture of failure specimens after bending test is shown in figure 7. The circle marked rupture on the bending specimens. As the fiber content increasing, the materials become brittle which could be ruptured during bending test.

Figure 7 Failure specimens after bending test

3.3 Izod impact property

The izod impact test was conducted to evaluate the impact property of these specimens. The Izod strength results of specimens with different fiber contents are shown in figure 8. It is found that as the fiber contents increasing, the Izod strength has decreased gradually for paper fiber or powder reinforced composite with fiber contents increasing. CP specimens has higher izod impact strength with PP specimens at same fiber contents. It is considered that longer fibers composite has better performance in impact test.

Figure 8 Izod strength of different fiber contents composite

The fracture of crushed paper fibers and paper powder composite was observed by SEM. The photos of failure specimens are illustrated in figure 9. From the observation, it was found that the fiber dispersion was not good after fabrication by direct fiber feeding injection molding process which has a big influence on mechanical property.

Figure 9 SEM observation on Izod specimens

3.4 Thermal conductivity test

In physics, thermal conductivity is the property of a material to conduct heat. It is evaluated primarily in terms of Fourier's Law for heat conduction. Heat transfer occurs at a lower rate across materials of low thermal conductivity than across materials of high thermal conductivity. Correspondingly, materials of high thermal conductivity are widely used in heat sink applications and materials of low thermal conductivity are used as thermal insulation. The thermal conductivity of a material may depend on temperature.

In this research, the thermal diffusivity and specific heat capacity was measured on different contents of paper materials to calculated conductivity. The measured results of pure PE are shown in figure 10. The temperature rising time is the main parameter to measure for measuring the thermal diffusivity and the temperature decreasing rate after maximum temperature is the main factor to measure for measuring the specific heat capacity. The thermal diffusivity could be obtained and together with specific heat the thermal conductivity could be calculated. The thermal diffusivity and specific heat capacity of PE are $2.75\text{E-}3 \text{ cm}^2/\text{sec}$ and $1.734 \text{ J}/(\text{g}\cdot\text{K})$. According to the formula (2), the thermal conductivity of PE is $0.455 \text{ W}/(\text{M}\cdot\text{K})$.

A. Temperature changing curve for thermal diffusivity measurement of PE

B. Temperature changing curve for specific heat capacity measurement of PE

Figure 10 Temperature measurement

The results of thermal conductivity with different paper contents are shown in figure 11. It was found that the thermal conductivity was increasing as the fiber contents slightly increased. It is considered that the PP type materials has better dispersion which caused higher thermal conductivity compared with CP type materials.

Figure 11 Thermal conductivity of different fiber contents composite

4 CONCLUSIONS

In this study, two kinds of recycled paper materials was used to fabricate composite by direct fiber feeding injection molding The poly ethylene (PE) was used as matrix injection molding process to fabricate composite. Mechanical property including tension, bending and Izod impact was tested and analyzed. The following conclusions were obtained.

1. From the tensile test, it was found that although the tensile property has slight increase, the materials become brittle as the fiber contents increased.
2. In bending test, crushed paper fiber and paper powder composite expressed similar property at same fiber contents.
3. The Izod impact strength decreased with the fiber contents increasing in paper fiber and paper powder reinforced composite. Due to the advantage of long fibers, crushed paper fiber composite has higher impact strength compared with paper powder reinforced composite at the same fiber contents.
4. The thermal conductivity was increasing as the fiber contents slightly increased from the thermal conductivity test. The PP type materials has better dispersion which caused higher thermal conductivity compared with CP type materials.

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